

Synthesis and biological evaluation of some new 4-aryl-1-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone by conventional and microwave methods and their biological activities

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Abstract : 4-Aryl-1-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone/4-aryl-3-chloro-1-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone were prepared by reaction of appropriate 2-(methoxy phenylideneamino)-4-diaryl pyrimidine (Schiff base) and acetyl chloride/chloroacetylchloride in dimethyl formamide (DMF). The reactions have been carried out by conventional, grindstone technique and microwave irradiation methods. The microwave irradiation method provided higher product yields in a very short period of time as compared to conventional method. All the prepared compounds were characterized by their elemental analysis and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR, Mass) data. The compounds have been evaluated for their spermicidal activity in semen of Holstein Friesian cattle, antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Keywords : 2-Azetidinone, Staudinger reaction, microwave irradiation, β -lactams.

Introduction

An advantage of solvent free reactions, in comparison to reaction in molecular solvents, is that the compounds formed are often sufficiently pure to circumvent extensive purification using chromatography. Many solvent free reactions are performed under microwave irradiation¹. The 2-azetidinone nucleus is well known for its pharmacological properties viz. anti-inflammatory, antidegenerative², antimicrobial³⁻⁶, antibiotics^{7,8} and several other biological activities like blood platelet aggregate inhibitors⁹.

Microwave irradiation, although occasionally known by such acronyms as 'MEC' (Microwave Enhanced Chemistry) or 'MORE' (Microwave organic reaction enhancement) is becoming an increasingly popular method of heating which replaces the classical one as it proves to be a clean, cheap and convenient method^{10,11}. This method of heating has been extended to almost all areas of organic chemistry¹². The microwave procedures for the synthesis of 2-azetidinones **4** and **5** owes its importance due to the fact that the reaction is complete within 180–250 s as compared to conventional method which requires 5–9

h heating.

Keeping in view of these observation we have now synthesized and characterized a series of substituted 2-azetidinones **4(a-j)** and **5(a-j)** (Scheme 1) by both conventional and microwave methods. A comparative study in terms of reaction time and yield of compounds under microwave and conventional methods is reported in table.

Biological activities :

Spermicidal activities : Sperm motility scheme¹³ was followed to see the effect of chemicals. Compounds **4a**, **4d**, **4e**, **4f**, **4h**, **5a**, **5d**, **5e**, **5f**, **5h** were evaluated for spermicidal activities, briefly the motility of sperms was observed under 40x magnification of light microscope in a cell counting chamber. While observing the motility, 25 μ l solution (compound + alcohol) was added to the 25 μ l semen and it was observed that addition of compounds **4** and **5** to semen produces a reduction of sperm motility in HF cattle spermatozoa; which was dose and time dependent. At 100 ppm concentration of compound **4f**, sperm motility was reduced to 25% in 2 min. Compound **4h** at 100 ppm inhibited motility to 50% in 4.5 min. After 4

Scheme 1

min sperm motility was reduced to 65% by compound **4a** where as **4d** and **4e** compounds reduces the motility to 35 and 55% respectively in 3–4 min at 100 ppm concentration only. The results have been summarized in graph (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Spermicidal activity.

Antimicrobial activity : The compounds have been evaluated for their antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum* at different concentration by disk diffusion method^{14,15}. Ampicillin and Mycostatin are used as reference compounds for evaluating antibacterial and antifungal activities, respectively. Compounds **4a**, **4d**, **4e**, **4h**, **4j**, **5a**, **5d**, **5e**, **5h**, **5j** showed enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activities at concentration 1000, 800, 400, 200 ppm due to the presence of chlorine atom in β -lactam ring. The results obtained are presented in Figs. 2 and 3.

Compounds with electron releasing groups such as methoxy and hydroxyl showed better antibacterial activity than the others not having such groups. Compounds having pharmacophores such as, chloro, bromo, fluoro, groups have exhibited more activity on all the three bacteria than the others. The activity of all the compounds evaluated has been found to be intense active towards *Staphylococcus aureus* than *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and

Escherichia coli (Fig. 2). Further with the introduction of two fluorine atoms compounds **4f** and **5f** become more active against all bacteria. Again the introduction of one more chlorine atom to the β -lactam ring of compound **4(a-j)** exhibit enhanced antibacterial activity. The study is conducted through 1000, 800, 400, 200 ppm concentration and compounds showed good results at 1000 ppm concentration.

Fig. 2. Antibacterial activity of 4-aryl-1-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone. IZ = Inhibition area excluding diameter of disk, AI = Activity index = inhibition area of sample/inhibition area of standard, A = *Staphylococcus aureus*, B = *Escherichia coli*, C = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Compounds : 1 = **4a**, 2 = **4d**, 3 = **4e**, 4 = **4f**, 5 = **4h**, 6 = **5a**, 7 = **5d**, 8 = **5e**, 9 = **5f**, 10 = **5h**.

These results suggest that the β -lactams and their derivatives have excellent scope for further development as commercial antimicrobial agents. Further experiments were needed to elucidate their mechanism of action.

Fig. 3. Antifungal activity of 4-aryl-1-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone. IZ = Inhibition area excluding diameter of disk, AI = Activity index = inhibition area of sample/inhibition area of standard, A = *Aspergillus niger*, B = *Fusarium oxysporum*, C = *Candida albicans*. Compounds : 1 = **4a**, 2 = **4d**, 3 = **4e**, 4 = **4f**, 5 = **4h**, 6 = **5a**, 7 = **5d**, 8 = **5e**, 9 = **5f**, 10 = **5h**.

Results and discussion

The IR spectrum of **2d** exhibited absorption peak in

the region 3330–3440 due to symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequencies of primary amine and another band at 1596 due to C=N. The disappearance of absorption band at 1680 due to C=O confirmed the involvement of CO-CH=CH functionality of **1d** in pyrimidine ring formation. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **2d** exhibited a broad singlet at 5.8 ppm due to methane proton on pyrimidine ring and a multiplet in the region of 7.5–8.4 was due to nine aromatic protons. Mass spectrum of **2d** exhibited the molecular ion peak M⁺ at *m/z* 316 equivalent to the molecular weight of **2d**. The same procedure was followed for compounds **2(a-j)**.

The IR spectrum of **3d** showed the disappearance of NH₂ band at 3330–3440 and appearance of a peak at 1620 band due to C=N. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **3d** displayed a multiplet in the region 6.8–8.1 due to nine aromatic protons and one methane proton which merged with aromatic protons. Further support for proposed structure is based on mass spectral studies.

In the IR spectra of compounds **4(a-j)** and **5(a-j)** disappearance of C=N bond at 1600–1610 cm⁻¹ and appearance of another carbonyl absorption band at 1700–1725 cm⁻¹ (unconjugated C=O) indicates the complete cyclisation of the Schiff bases **3d** into 2-azetidinone and its chloro derivative.

In addition to this appearance of a triplet for -CH₂ protons, a doublet for -CH protons of azetidinone ring between δ 2–4 ppm in the ¹H NMR confirms the formation of compound **4(a-j)**. All the aromatic proton resonance signals are spread over δ 6.9–8.5 ppm. ¹H NMR spectra of compound **5(a-j)** exhibited a double doublet of the two hydrogen on the azetidinone ring in the region δ 2.8–3.5 ppm. All the compounds have also been characterized by mass spectral studies by their molecular ion peak 516 and 550.5 for **4d** and **5d** respectively which correspond to their molecular weights. Spectral data of compounds **4(a-j)** and **5(a-j)** are in harmony with proposed structures.

Table 1. Analytical datas of substituted 2-pyrimidines **2(a-j)**

Comps.	X	Y	Mol. wt.	M.p.	Mol. formula	Time		Yield (%)		Elemental analysis (%) :		
						M.W.	Con.	M.W.	Con.	Found (Calcd.)		
										(s)	(h)	C
2a	4-OCH ₃	4-F	256	170	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ OF	250	14	75	65	69.10 (69.15)	4.72 (4.74)	14.20 (14.23)
2b	4-OCH ₃	4-H	238	275	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	200	13	70	50	73.31 (73.33)	5.37 (5.39)	15.09 (15.10)
2c	4-F	4-H	226	278	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ F	210	12	69	60	72.44 (72.45)	4.51 (4.52)	15.81 (15.84)
2d	4-OCH ₃	4-Br	317	170	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ OBr	230	13	79	68	57.12 (57.14)	3.90 (3.92)	11.75 (11.76)
2e	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	311.5	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ OCl	190	13	72	68	65.47 (65.48)	4.47 (4.49)	13.46 (13.48)
2f	4-F	4-F	283	180	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ F ₂	220	14	68	50	67.81 (67.84)	3.86 (3.88)	14.83 (14.84)
2g	4-Cl	4-F	299.5	165	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ FCl	205	13	65	45	64.08 (64.10)	3.65 (3.67)	14.01 (14.02)
2h	Furyl	4-Br	314	210	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₃ OBr	180	14	76	68	53.48 (53.50)	2.52 (2.54)	13.35 (13.37)
2i	Furyl	4-F	253	170	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₃ OF	210	13	68	60	66.37 (66.40)	3.14 (3.16)	16.58 (16.60)
2j	Furyl	4-Cl	269.5	180	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₃ OCl	220	14	72	68	62.32 (62.33)	2.95 (2.96)	15.56 (15.58)

Experimental

General : Melting points were determined in open glass capillary tube and are uncorrected. IR spectra (cm^{-1}) were recorded on FTIR Nicolet Magna 550 and Shimadzu 8400S spectrophotometer in KBr disc and noteworthy absorptions levels (cm^{-1}) were listed. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL AL 300 MHz FT NMR instrument, ν in cm^{-1} . Mass spectra were determined by JEOL SX-102 spectrometer. Microwave irradiation was carried out in a Samsung m 1630N/M 1610 W household microwave oven with maximum 600 W power. TLC using silica gel G as adsorbent checked the purity of the compounds, UV light or iodine accomplished visualization.

1,3-(4-Fluoroaryl)-2-propene-1-one and other substituted chalcones were prepared by literature method^{16,17}.

Synthesis of 2-amino-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine 2(a-j) :

Conventional method : To a refluxing mixture of 1,3-diaryl-2-propene-1-one (**1**) (0.01 mol) and guanidine nitrate (0.01 mol, 1.22 g) in rectified spirit (50 ml), aq.

sodium hydroxide (40%, 5 ml) was added portion-wise during a period of 3 h and refluxing continued for 12 h. Completion of reaction was checked by TLC. The solvent was distilled off and the reaction mixture was diluted with distilled water. The resulting solid was collected and crystallized from distilled benzene. Yield 50–68%.

Microwave method : A mixture of 1,3-diaryl-2-propene-1-one (**1**) (0.01 mol) and guanidine nitrate (0.01 mol, 1.22 g) and sodium ethoxide was taken in a conical flask. The mixture was irradiated in a microwave oven for about 3–4 min. It was poured onto the crushed ice. The solid product thus formed was filtered, dried and recrystallized from rectified spirit. Following same procedure, the compounds **2(a-j)** were prepared. Yield 65–79%.

Synthesis of 2-(4-methoxy benzylidene)-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine 3(a-j) :

Conventional method : Substituted Schiff's base of series **3(a-j)** as shown in Table 2 were synthesised by re-

Table 2. Analytical datas of substituted Schiff's bases **3(a-j)**

Compds.	X	Y	Mol. wt.	M.p.	Mol. formula	Time		Yield (%)		Elemental analysis (%) :		
						M.W.	Con.	M.W.	Con.	Found (Calcd.)		
						(s)	(h)			C	H	N
3a	4-OCH ₃	4-F	413	135	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ F	30	2	69	65	72.60 (72.63)	4.81 (4.84)	10.13 (10.16)
3b	4-OCH ₃	4-H	396	220	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	25	3	55	45	75.72 (75.75)	5.28 (5.30)	10.59 (10.60)
3c	4-F	4-H	383	320	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₃ OF	28	1	75	70	75.15 (75.19)	4.65 (4.69)	10.95 (10.96)
3d	4-OCH ₃	4-Br	475	160	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Br	35	0.5	80	75	63.14 (63.15)	4.20 (4.21)	8.80 (8.84)
3e	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	429.5	170	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	27	2	71	68	69.82 (69.84)	4.62 (4.65)	9.74 (9.77)
3f	4-F	4-F	401	180	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ OF ₂	22	1.5	73	67	71.80 (71.82)	4.20 (4.23)	10.45 (10.47)
3g	4-Cl	4-F	417.5	165	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ FOCl	26	3	76	62	68.95 (68.98)	4.03 (4.07)	10.02 (10.05)
3h	Furyl	4-Br	432	160	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Br	45	1	61	55	61.10 (61.11)	3.22 (3.24)	9.70 (9.72)
3i	Furyl	4-F	371	140	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ F	38	1.5	63	58	71.12 (71.15)	3.75 (3.77)	11.31 (11.32)
3j	Furyl	4-Cl	387.5	135	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	40	1.5	64	52	68.09 (68.12)	3.60 (3.61)	10.80 (10.83)

fluxing substituted pyrimidines (0.01 mol) of series **2(a-j)** with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in 10 ml of dried and distilled ethanol using water bath for one hour. Double distilled water was added dropwise until a slight cloudiness persists and kept the solution on one side to cool. The solid deposited by filtration was collected and washed well with cold aqueous ethanol, 88% of air dried crude Schiff base is obtained which is sufficiently pure for conversion into the amine. A small portion was crystallised from aqueous methanol. Same procedure was followed for synthesis of compounds of series **3(a-j)**. The percentage yield was observed to be 52–68% for pyrimidines.

Microwave method : In a typical preparation, mixture of 4-methoxy benzaldehyde (1.0 mm) and 2-(4-methoxy benzylidene)-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine **2(a-j)** (1.0 mm) in rectified spirit were taken in a flask capped with funnel placed in a microwave oven and irradiated at 500 watt for 30 s. After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC), the resultant mixture was allowed to attain room tempera-

ture. The solvent was removed and residue recrystallized from distilled methanol was to afford the Schiff's bases **3(a-j)** by using respective pyrimidines. Yield 61–80%.

Synthesis of 4-aryl-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone series 4(a-j) :

Conventional method : To the 10 ml of stirring dimethyl formamide (DMF), 2 mmol of acetyl chloride, 2 mmol of triethylamine and 2 mmol of azomethine i.e. 2-(4-methoxy benzylidene)-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine were added, solution was heated to reflux for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with 50 ml of water and was extracted with 25 ml of dichloromethane or chloroform. The organic layer was dried and evaporated in vacuum. It afforded oil or a crystalline residue, which after recrystallisation from ethanol afforded β -lactams. The percentage yield was observed to be 60–70% for various azetidinones as shown in Table 3.

Microwave method : A mixture of 2-(4-methoxy benzylidene)-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine (0.01 mol) in DMF was taken in a conical flask and acetyl chloride (0.01 mol)

Table 3. Analytical datas of substituted 2-azetidinones **4(a-j)**

Comps.	X	Y	Mol. wt.	M.p.	Mol. formula	Time		Yield (%)		Elemental analysis (%) :		
						M.W.	Con.	M.W.	Con.	Found (Calcd.)		
										C	H	N
4a	4-OCH ₃	4-F	455	115	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₃ F	180	10	73	68	71.17 (71.20)	4.80 (4.83)	9.27 (9.23)
4b	4-OCH ₃	4-H	437	128	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃	200	9	65	60	74.10 (74.14)	5.21 (5.26)	9.58 (9.61)
4c	4-F	4-H	425	180	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ FO ₂	190	10	72	65	73.40 (73.41)	4.68 (4.70)	9.85 (9.88)
4d	4-OCH ₃	4-Br	517	190	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₃ Br	160	8	74	62	62.63 (62.66)	4.21 (4.25)	8.09 (8.12)
4e	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	471.5	138	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	210	9	76	69	68.68 (68.71)	4.62 (4.66)	8.04 (8.09)
4f	4-F	4-F	443	185	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ F ₂ O ₂	170	11	67	58	70.38 (70.42)	4.25 (4.28)	9.42 (9.48)
4g	4-Cl	4-F	459.5	160	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ FO ₂ Cl	190	10	62	56	67.84 (67.89)	4.10 (4.13)	9.12 (9.14)
4h	Furyl	4-Br	474	155	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ Br	210	9	75	70	60.70 (60.75)	3.34 (3.37)	8.82 (8.86)
4i	Furyl	4-F	413	166	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ F	225	10	70	66	69.69 (69.73)	3.85 (3.87)	10.14 (10.16)
4j	Furyl	4-Cl	429.5	170	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	200	10	76	69	67.01 (67.05)	3.69 (3.72)	9.73 (9.77)

and trimethylamine (0.01 mol) were added slowly. The mixture was irradiated in a microwave oven for about 3–4 min. It was then diluted with ice cold water. The solid product thus formed was filtered, dried and recrystallized from rectified spirit. Following same procedure, the compounds **4(a-j)** were prepared. The percentage yield was observed to be 62–76% for various azetidinones as shown in Table 3.

Spectral data :

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4a**) : m.p. 115 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3240 (NH), 1725 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.2 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.9 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 454 $[\text{M}]^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-phenyl-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4b**) : m.p. 128 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3220 (NH), 1705 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.7 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 436 $[\text{M}]^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-phenyl-6-(4-fluorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4c**) : m.p. 180 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3210 (NH), 1715 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.1 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.8 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 424 $[\text{M}]^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-phenyl-6-(4-fluorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4c**) : m.p. 180 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3225 (NH), 1710 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.3 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.7 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 424 $[\text{M}]^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-bromophenyl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4d**) : m.p. 190 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1720 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.4 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.6 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 516 $[\text{M}]^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4e**) : m.p. 138 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3225 (NH), 1715 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$),

Table 4. Analytical datas of substituted 3-chloro-2-azetidinones **5(a-j)**

Compds.	X	Y	Mol. wt.	M.p.	Mol. formula	Time		Yield (%)		Elemental analysis (%) :		
						M.W.	Con.	M.W.	Con.	Found (Calcd.)		
										(s)	(h)	C
5a	4-OCH ₃	4-F	489.5	110	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ FCl	190	8	75	63	66.15 (66.18)	4.25 (4.29)	8.53 (8.58)
5b	4-OCH ₃	4-H	472.5	125	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	210	9	71	69	68.53 (68.57)	4.60 (4.65)	8.85 (8.88)
5c	4-F	4-H	459.5	169	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ FO ₂ Cl	170	10	73	67	67.85 (67.89)	4.10 (4.13)	9.10 (9.14)
5d	4-OCH ₃	4-Br	551.5	185	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ BrCl	150	9	86	80	58.72 (58.74)	3.79 (3.80)	7.59 (7.61)
5e	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	506	142	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂	220	9	63	59	64.00 (64.03)	4.12 (4.15)	8.25 (8.30)
5f	4-F	4-F	477.5	137	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₃ F ₂ O ₂ Cl	180	8	60	56	65.31 (65.34)	3.71 (3.76)	8.75 (8.79)
5g	4-Cl	4-F	494	126	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₃ FO ₂ Cl ₂	215	10	59	55	63.10 (63.15)	3.61 (3.64)	8.47 (8.50)
5h	Furyl	4-Br	508.5	1.36	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ BrCl	230	9	69	62	56.60 (56.63)	2.92 (2.94)	8.21 (8.25)
5i	Furyl	4-F	447.5	145	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ FCl	200	10	73	67	64.32 (64.35)	3.31 (3.35)	9.33 (9.38)
5j	Furyl	4-Cl	464	135	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂	210	10	80	71	62.03 (62.06)	3.20 (3.23)	9.02 (9.05)

3.8 (1H, t, -CH), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 470 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(4-fluorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4f**) : m.p. 185 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3235 (NH), 1705 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.3 (2H, d, -CH₂), 3.7 (1H, t, -CH), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 442 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4g**) : m.p. 160 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3210 (NH), 1720 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.2 (2H, d, -CH₂), 3.6 (1H, t, -CH), 7.1–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 458 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-bromophenyl)-6-furylpyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4h**) : m.p. 155 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3225 (NH), 1705 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.3 (2H, d, -CH₂), 3.5 (1H, t, -CH), 7.1–7.9 (12H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 473 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-furylpyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4i**) : m.p. 166 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1715 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.1 (2H, d, -CH₂), 3.7 (1H, t, -CH), 7.1–7.9 (12H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 412 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-1-[4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-furylpyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**4j**) : m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3249 (NH), 1710 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.4 (2H, d, -CH₂), 3.9 (1H, t, -CH), 7.1–7.9 (12H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 428 [M]⁺.

Synthesis of 4-aryl-3-chloro-1-(4,6-diaryl pyrimidine)-2-azetidinone 5(a-j) :

Conventional method : To the 10 ml of stirring distilled dimethyl formamide (DMF), 2 mmol of chloroacetyl chloride, 2 mmol of triethylamine and 2 mmol of azomethine i.e. 2-(4-methoxy benzylidene)-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine were added, solution was heated to reflux for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with 50 ml of distilled water and was extracted with 25 ml of distilled dichloromethane or chloroform. The organic layer was dried and evaporated in vacuum. It afforded oil or a crystalline residue, which after recrystallisation from rectified spirit afforded β -lactams.

Microwave method : A mixture of 2-(4-methoxy-

benzylidene)-4,6-diaryl pyrimidine (0.01 mol) in distilled DMF was taken in a conical flask and chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) and trimethylamine (0.01 mol) were added slowly. The mixture was irradiated in a microwave oven for about 3–4 min. It was then diluted with ice cold water. The solid product thus formed was filtered, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit. Following same procedure, the compounds **5(a-j)** were prepared.

Spectral data :

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5a**) : m.p. 110 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 488.5 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-phenyl-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5b**) : m.p. 125 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 471.5 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-phenyl-6-(4-fluorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5c**) : m.p. 169 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 458.5 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-bromophenyl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5d**) : m.p. 185 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 550.5 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5e**) : m.p. 142 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 505 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(4-fluorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5f**) : m.p. 137 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ¹H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 476.5 [M]⁺.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)pyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5g**) : m.p. 126 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 493 [M] $^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-bromophenyl)-6-furylpyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5h**) : m.p. 136 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 507.5 [M] $^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-furylpyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5i**) : m.p. 145 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 446.5 [M] $^+$.

4-Methoxyphenyl-3-chloro-1-[4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-furylpyrimidine]-2-azetidinone (**5j**) : m.p. 135 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.0–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-R); MS (m/z) : 463 [M] $^+$.

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